

ISic3096

I.Sicily inscription 3096

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331421

1. . . . [τελευ]-

2. τᾶ τῆς δ [έκα — — —]

3. Ὀκτωβρ[ίου ὑπ(ατία) Βιν]-

4. κεν (τίου) □ ἰ (νδικτίωνι) □ π (εντεκαίδεκα) ²⁷ἰ(μέρα) [or τ(ῆ)] π(αρασκευῆ)
(?)²⁷

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645444

PHI 331421

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-

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